

How Painting Associates with Blood in Urine?

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DOI: <http://doi.org/10.38177/AJBSR.2022.4306>

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Article Received: 15 May 2022

Article Accepted: 21 August 2022

Article Published: 27 September 2022

ABSTRACT

If someone is painting lover then there must be chances that he/she is standing most of the time and can have chances of blood in urine. Blood release through urine known as hematuria. Gross hematuria is a condition in which we see the release of blood with urine. Microscopic hematuria is a condition in which we can't see the blood release in urine. Kidney infection, bladder stone, excess walk and cancer are the main cause of hematuria. Age and family history are the main risk factor. Building block of painting is the basic elements of painting. There are six basic elements of painting which are color, tone, line, shape, space and texture. The heart of painting is color. Every color has many shades and tones. By playing with texture painting is the best medium. Those who have blood in their urine have lowest percentage regarding to like painting and those who have no blood in their urine have highest percentage level towards likeliness of painting.

Keywords: Hematuria, Blood test, Stone formation, Painting and family history.

1. Introduction

When blood release through urine known as hematuria. Gross hematuria is a condition in which we see the release of blood with urine. Microscopic hematuria is a condition in which we can't see the blood release in urine. Kidney infection, bladder stone, excess walk and cancer are the main cause of hematuria. Age and family history are the main risk factor. Chill, fever, nausea and vomiting are the main symptoms. To prevent this disease we avoid to intake alcohols and chemicals. Through blood test and CT scan we can check hematuria.

Building block of painting is the basic elements of painting. There are six basic elements of painting which are color, tone, line, shape, space and texture. The heart of painting is color. Every color plays a vital role in painting. Every color has many shades and tones.

In grayscale the tone is seen well. Every brushstroke is important because every line indicates new idea. An artist makes a whole story with different shapes in the painting. In painting positive and negative spaces are present which is very crucial for an artist. By playing with texture painting is the best medium. If someone is painting lover then there must be chances that he is standing most of the time and can have chances of blood in urine. The scientific worker has already been co-relate different parameter of a specific topic (1-5).

Aim of this study is to co-relate painting with blood in urine.

2. Materials and Methods

Sum of all students is 100 which participate in this project from Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan.

2.1. Hematuria

Blood in urine can be check by Hematuria through CT-scan and MRI test. Any infection in urethra can be scan through "cystoscopy". In this technique a small camera is linked with a thread which passes within the bladder.

2.2. Study Design

A questionnaire was already trained about painting.

3. Results and Discussion

Relation between the painting and blood in urine is given in table given below. The percentage of male is calculated. From all male participants 60% male have no blood in their urine while 10% male have blood in their urine and have fond of painting. Those who are antagonist of painting have 0% blood in urine while 30% have blood in their urine. Just like in male, those female who have fond of painting have 8.75% blood in their urine and 53.75% have no blood in their urine while those female who are antagonist of painting have 3.75% blood in their urine and 33.75% have no blood in their urine.

Table 1. Association of painting with Blood in urine

Gender	Fond of painting		Antagonist of painting	
	Blood in urine	No blood in urine	Blood in urine	No blood in urine
Male	10%	60%	0%	30%
Female	8.75%	53.75%	3.75%	33.75%

Questionnaire based study has been important outcome in current researches. There are some previous study in which painting has connection with different researches like blood group, pulse rate etc. The scientific worker has already been co-relate different parameter of a specific topic.

4. Conclusion

From above experiment it was concluded that those who have no blood in their urine have highest percentage towards likeliness of painting in both male and female. Those who have blood in their urine have lowest percentage towards likeliness of painting.

Declarations

Source of Funding

This research did not receive any grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare no competing financial, professional, and personal interests.

Ethical Approval

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan.

Consent for publication

Authors declare that they consented for the publication of this research work.

Availability of data and material

Authors are willing to share the data and material according to relevant needs.

Authors' Contributions

All authors equally contributed to data collection, research, and paper drafting.

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